

Study of Screening Method of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (DIPSI Criteria) at Tertiary Care HospitalNalini I. Anand¹, P. S. Punatar², Arman M. Mansuri³¹Professor and Head, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Shri M.P. Shah Govt. Medical College, Jamnagar, Gujarat²Additional Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Shri M.P. Shah Govt. Medical College, Jamnagar, Gujarat³Second Year Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Shri M.P. Shah Govt. Medical College, Jamnagar, Gujarat

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a pregnancy-related medical complication linked to significant maternal and fetal risks. Several screening methods are available for detecting GDM, including the DIPSI criteria, which use a non-fasting, single-step test measuring 2-hour plasma glucose levels after administering 75 grams of glucose. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of this one-step screening and diagnostic procedure and identify high-risk factors for GDM in the study population.**Material and Methods:** This prospective study was conducted over a 6-month period, involving 4050 antenatal women attending the outpatient department (OPD) with gestational ages between 24 to 28 weeks. All participants underwent the DIPSI screening test with 75 grams of oral glucose, regardless of their last meal. A structured questionnaire was also administered to collect data on potential risk factors for GDM.**Results:** The prevalence of GDM, based on the DIPSI criteria, was found to be 9.9%. Identified high-risk factors included age >30 years, previous history of GDM, history of GCA (gestational carbohydrate intolerance), prior birth weight >4 kg, and family history of diabetes.**Conclusions:** The DIPSI criteria offer a non-fasting, single-step approach to screening and diagnosing GDM, making it a simple, cost-effective, and evidence-based method. Its user-friendly nature and feasibility are particularly beneficial in resource-limited settings, improving accessibility and early detection of GDM.**Keywords:** DIPSI, GDM, OPD, OGTT.

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Introduction

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) is characterized by carbohydrate intolerance of varying severity, first detected during pregnancy. Despite efforts by international organizations to establish diagnostic criteria, no universally accepted standard has been reached. [1] The significance of GDM lies in its intergenerational impact, as it increases the risk of diabetes in both the mother and her child. [2] Women with a history of GDM are more likely to develop type 2 diabetes in the future, and their children are also at higher risk of metabolic complications. [3] Moreover, any form of glucose intolerance during pregnancy, even if not diagnosed as GDM, can lead to adverse fetal outcomes. [4] Evidence shows that rising levels of maternal carbohydrate intolerance are associated with progressively worse maternal and fetal outcomes. [5] Indian women, due to genetic susceptibility, are particularly prone to developing diabetes during pregnancy. Recognizing this public

health concern, the Government of India has mandated universal screening for glucose intolerance in pregnancy. [6] As per the guidelines, all pregnant women should undergo screening between 24 and 28 weeks of gestation using a 75-gram oral glucose challenge test (GCT), with plasma glucose levels measured two hours after consumption. [7] This comprehensive approach to screening ensures the early detection and management of GDM, aiming to improve both maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted over a period of six months at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Guru Govind Singh Hospital, Jamnagar, Gujarat. A total of 4050 antenatal women attending the outpatient department (OPD) were enrolled in the study after meeting the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. The aim

was to identify and manage cases of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) using standardized screening procedures. The study included pregnant women with a gestational age between 24 and 28 weeks. Women who were known cases of diabetes mellitus, those on steroid therapy, or those unwilling to participate were excluded. This ensured that only new cases of GDM could be identified, eliminating any confounding factors from pre-existing diabetes or other metabolic conditions.

All eligible participants underwent a glucose challenge test (GCT), following the Diabetes in Pregnancy Study Group India (DIPSI) criteria. Each participant was given 75 grams of glucose dissolved in 250-300 ml of water, irrespective of the timing of their last meal. Two hours after consumption, plasma glucose levels were measured. A cutoff value of ≥ 140 mg/dl was used to diagnose GDM, ensuring early identification and appropriate management of glucose intolerance during pregnancy.

While the primary screening was performed between 24 and 28 weeks of gestation, recent research emphasizes the need for earlier screening.

It is now understood that fetal beta cells begin to respond to maternal glucose levels as early as the 16th week of pregnancy. Therefore, it is recommended that glucose screening be initiated during the first trimester, particularly for women with high-risk factors. If the first test is negative, repeat screening is suggested around 24-28 weeks, with a final test between 32 and 34 weeks to ensure no cases are missed. This stepwise screening approach ensures that all cases of GDM are promptly identified, allowing timely interventions to minimize risks to both mother and child. Early detection of glucose intolerance enables better glycemic control and reduces the likelihood of adverse maternal and fetal outcomes.

Results

The study population predominantly consisted of women aged 21-30 years (82.6%), with a mean age of 24.3 ± 3.56 years and an interquartile range of 22-26 years. GDM prevalence, as assessed using DIPSI criteria with 75g OGTT, was found to be 9.9% (402/4050). Monthly screening revealed varying GDM cases, with the highest number of positive cases in January (76) and the lowest in May (58). (Table 1)

Figure 1: Age distribution (%)

Table 1: Distribution of Participants Tested by 75g OGTT and GDM Positive Cases

Month	Tested by 75g OGTT	GDM Positive
January	599 (14.79%)	76 (12.7%)
February	507 (12.52%)	74 (14.6%)
March	695 (17.16%)	68 (9.8%)
April	565 (13.95%)	64 (11.3%)
May	834 (20.59%)	58 (7.0%)
June	850 (20.99%)	62 (7.3%)
Total	4050 (100%)	402 (9.9%)

Among high-risk factors, 7.16% of participants were above 30 years, 40% had a history of GDM in a previous pregnancy, and 20% had prior pregnancies with either GCA or birth weights exceeding 4 kg. Additionally, 25.31% of participants had a family history of diabetes

mellitus, indicating a significant genetic predisposition within the population. These findings emphasize the importance of early screening and tailored interventions to manage GDM effectively.

Table 2: Risk Factors in GDM Population

Risk Factor	Total Study Population (n)	GDM Cases (n) with Percentage
Age > 30 years	340	93 (27.35%)
Family history of diabetes	391	99 (25.31%)
Previous history of GDM	25	10 (40%)
History of GCA	96	26 (27%)
Birth weight > 4 kg in previous pregnancy	25	5 (20%)

Figure 2 highlights the prevalence of GDM across different BMI categories, showing that the highest prevalence (38.7%) is observed in women with a BMI of 30 or higher, suggesting a strong association between higher BMI and GDM risk.

Figure 2: Prevalence of GDM by BMI (%)

The prevalence of GDM showed a clear increasing trend with advancing age, starting from 15.2% in the 15-19 years group and rising to 27.3% in those aged ≥30 years. This positive age-related trend was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that older maternal age is associated with a higher risk of GDM. (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Prevalence of GDM by Age Group (%)

Table 3: Comparison of Various Criteria for Diagnosis of GDM

Criteria	Method	Fasting (mg/dl)	1 hr (mg/dl)	2 hr (mg/dl)	3 hr (mg/dl)
WHO	Fasting 75 g OGTT	≥ 126	-	≥ 140	-
IADPSG	Fasting 75 g OGTT	≥ 92	≥ 180	≥ 153	-
DIPSI	Non-fasting 75 g OGTT	-	-	≥ 140	-
ADA	Fasting 100 g OGTT	95	100	155	140

The table 3 compares the diagnostic criteria for GDM used by different organizations. The WHO and IADPSG use fasting 75g OGTT with different thresholds, while the DIPSI protocol uses a non-fasting 75g OGTT focusing on 2-hour glucose levels. The ADA, on the other hand, employs a 100g OGTT with multiple glucose checks across 1, 2, and 3 hours.

Discussion

Increasing levels of maternal hyperglycemia during pregnancy are directly linked to higher rates of pregnancy-related complications and a heightened risk of future diabetes in mothers. Beyond maternal health, hyperglycemia also affects fetal development, particularly the pancreas, increasing the infant's vulnerability to diabetes later in life, irrespective of genetic predispositions. The HAPO (Hyperglycemia and Adverse Pregnancy Outcome) study demonstrated that even glucose levels below the diagnostic threshold for gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) were associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes. [8] Based on these findings, the IADPSG (International Association of Diabetes and Pregnancy Study Groups) revised the diagnostic criteria for GDM to reflect the impact of elevated glucose on pregnancy outcomes. [9]

In our study, the prevalence of GDM was 9.9% using the DIPSI criteria. This aligns closely with the findings of Swaroop et al. [10], who reported a similar prevalence of 9.7% using the same DIPSI methodology in a rural tertiary setting in Uttar Pradesh. [10] Similarly, Ghanghoriya et al. [11] observed a slightly lower prevalence of 9.4% in their cohort using the DIPSI guidelines, reinforcing that GDM detection through single-step non-fasting glucose tests is both feasible and effective in diverse settings.

A study by Phulpagar et al. [12] reported a lower prevalence of 8.7% in their study conducted in Mumbai, also using the DIPSI criteria. Notably, their research highlights the simplicity and accessibility of this method, making it ideal for resource-limited environments. In comparison, Soni et al. [13] identified a higher prevalence of 11.2% at a tertiary care center in Amritsar, with increased incidence noted among multiparous women and those with BMI >27.5. This slight variation suggests that geographical, demographic, and lifestyle factors influence GDM prevalence across different regions in India. GDM is considered one of the most significant metabolic

disorders during pregnancy, necessitating timely detection and management. However, traditional diagnostic methods, which require fasting, can pose challenges for pregnant women, especially those traveling long distances or residing in resource-limited settings. A non-fasting, single-step procedure, as proposed by the Diabetes in Pregnancy Study Group India (DIPSI), provides a more practical alternative. DIPSI recommends diagnosing GDM using a 2-hour post-glucose (75 g) plasma glucose value ≥ 140 mg/dL (7.8 mmol/L), regardless of the last meal. [14] This simplified approach has gained widespread popularity in India due to its convenience and accessibility.

In terms of risk factors, our study identified previous history of GDM (40%) as the most common, followed by BMI >30 (38.7%) and age >30 years (27.35%). These findings are consistent with the patterns observed by Soni et al. [13], who also highlighted maternal age and elevated BMI as significant contributors to GDM development. The overlap in these findings supports the need for targeted screening of high-risk groups.

Additionally, Phulpagar et al. [12] reported a higher rate of adverse outcomes among GDM patients, such as macrosomia (33.33%) and increased cesarean sections (30%) compared to non-GDM groups, reinforcing the importance of early detection and management. Similarly, Ghanghoriya et al. [11] noted that all newborns weighing more than 4 kg were born to mothers with GDM, emphasizing the direct impact of maternal glucose levels on neonatal outcomes.

Our study's findings further align with the results of Singh et al. [15], who found that using DIPSI criteria for GDM screening yields comparable results to other methods, including IADPSG, but with greater ease of implementation in the Indian context. The similar rates and risk factors identified across these studies underline the value of adopting standardized, efficient screening methods like DIPSI in both urban and rural healthcare settings.

Our study emphasizes the utility of this non-fasting 75g glucose challenge test as both a screening and diagnostic tool for GDM. The findings align with the American Diabetes Association (ADA)'s recommendations regarding the practicality and efficacy of simplified screening methods. [16] A study by Seshiah V et al. [17] in India compared the DIPSI guidelines with the IADPSG criteria,

reporting GDM prevalence rates of 14.6% (214 cases) with DIPSI and 13.4% (196 cases) with IADPSG. The minor differences between the two criteria were statistically insignificant ($p = 0.21$) based on McNemar's test, indicating close agreement between the methods. Another relevant study by Wery et al. [18] examined the impact of the revised IADPSG thresholds by conducting universal screening on 200 consecutive pregnant women between 24 and 28 weeks using a 75 g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT). This study reported a GDM prevalence rate of 14.0%, demonstrating that the new IADPSG criteria identified more cases than previous standards. These findings suggest that the updated IADPSG thresholds may contribute to earlier and more comprehensive identification of GDM cases. [19]

In our study, past history of GDM (40%) emerged as the most common risk factor among women diagnosed with GDM, followed by BMI >30 (38.7%), age >30 years (27.35%), and family history of diabetes (25.31%). These findings highlight the importance of screening for GDM, particularly among women with these high-risk characteristics. Our study reinforces the utility of DIPSI criteria for screening and diagnosing GDM. [15] Consistent with findings from other studies, the identified risk factors, such as age, BMI, and history of GDM, highlight the importance of proactive screening, especially in high-risk populations. The comparative insights from other research further validate our approach, demonstrating that timely intervention can significantly improve maternal and fetal outcomes.

Our study has certain limitations. Being a hospital-based study, the findings may not fully represent the broader population. Additionally, the reliance on the DIPSI criteria, while convenient, may result in some false-negative or false-positive cases compared to more stringent methods like IADPSG. We also did not assess the long-term outcomes of GDM in mothers and neonates, which could provide deeper insights into the effectiveness of early detection and management.

Conclusion

Our study supports the use of the DIPSI criteria as an effective, practical, and economical approach for diagnosing GDM in the Indian context. The non-fasting, single-step glucose challenge test offers a convenient solution, particularly for pregnant women who often need to travel long distances for healthcare visits. Consistent with findings from other studies, we identified key risk factors such as previous history of GDM, BMI >30, and maternal age >30 years, emphasizing the importance of targeted screening among high-risk groups. The simplicity and feasibility of DIPSI make it a reliable alternative to more resource-intensive

methods like IADPSG, while achieving comparable diagnostic accuracy. Early detection through universal screening and a thorough medical history ensures better glycemic control and reduces the risk of maternal and neonatal complications, ultimately improving outcomes. The adoption of such standardized screening methods remains crucial in preventing long-term health risks, including diabetes in both mother and child.

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